

ISic0266

I.Sicily inscription 0266

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object

tabula

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Alex Antoniou,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Messana

Place of origin (modern)

Messina

Provenance

Largo di Chiesa di San Giovanni Gerosolimitano Di Malta

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Messina, Museo regionale interdisciplinare di Messina, inventory A3563

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Dis · Man[ibus]
2. Epitynch[ani] · [Caes](aris)
3. n(ostri) ser(vi) Cand[idian](i)
4. qui exiebat · i[nofficio]
5. Asiae · ark(arii) XX [· hered](itatium)

Apparatus

Text based upon Bitto 2001 and photograph

Translation (en)

To the shades of the underworld, Epitynchanus Candidianus, slave of our Caesar, died en route to Asia to take up office of treasurer of the 5% inheritance tax.

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 284758

EDR 033598

EDCS 21900296

PHI 313664

Bibliography

Mommsen, Th. 1883. *Inscriptiones Bruttiorum Lucaniae Campaniae Siciliae Sardiniae Latinae. Pars posterior. Inscriptiones Siciliae et Sardiniae. Corpus Inscriptionum Latinarum, consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae editum.* Berlin. At 10.6977 (<http://arachne.uni-koeln.de/books/CILv10pII1883>)

Bitto, I. 2001. *Le iscrizioni greche e latine di Messina. Pelorias 7.* Messina. At 32

Dessau, H. 1892-1916. *Inscriptiones Latinae Selectae.* Berlin. At 1558

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Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-17): ISic0266. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4334801>